

BASIC PHARMACOLOGY OF NEW ORAL ANTICOAGULANTS AND ITS CLINICAL PROFILE: AN INCISIVE REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

The direct oral anticoagulants (DOACs) or novel oral anticoagulants (NOACs) are the non-vitamin K antagonist anticoagulants, which are relatively newer in the market. They include oral direct thrombin and factor X inhibitors. The approved indications are stroke prevention, treatment and prevention of venous thromboembolism, and coronary artery disease treatment. Although, recent studies have showed that the NOACs have better safety profile, convenient to administer, and less food and drug interactions compared to current oral anticoagulants. Clinicians prefer to prescribe traditional oral anticoagulants such as warfarin in the clinical setting. Thus, the aim of this review is to discuss the pharmacological properties of DOACs, efficacy and safety profile, laboratory-monitoring tests, and current reversal agents, focusing on the latest evidence from the subclinical and clinical trials.

KEYWORDS: Direct oral anticoagulants, pharmacotherapy, reversal agents.

INTRODUCTION

Venous thromboembolism (VTE) is a major burden on the healthcare system. The annual incidence of venous thromboembolism is approximately 108 per 100,000 person-year.^[1] For decades, vitamin K antagonists e.g. warfarin are widely used for long-term prevention and treatment of venous thromboembolism. However, they have some limitations, such as high therapeutic index, drug and food interactions, inpatient and interpatient variability, and the need for frequent laboratory monitoring.^[2] The DOACs have resolved these issues to some remarkable extent. This class of medication is non-vitamin K oral anticoagulants that directly inhibit specific coagulation factors.^[3] Currently, there are five agents approved via the FDA for clinical use namely, dabigatran etexilate (Pradaxa), rivaroxaban (Xarelto), apixaban (Eliquis), edoxaban (Savaysa), and betrixaban (Bevyxxa).^[4, 5] Dabigatran was the first direct thrombin (II) inhibitor that approved on 2010.^[6, 7] Rivaroxaban, apixaban, edoxaban, and betrixaban are direct factor X inhibitors, which approved on 2011, 2012, 2015, and 2017 respectively.^[7] They have replaced low-molecular-weight heparins for thromboprophylaxis in patients undergo elective hip or knee arthroplasty and replaced warfarin for stroke prevention in patients with nonvalvular atrial fibrillation, and treatment of venous thromboembolism.^[8, 9] The benefits of these agents include wide therapeutic window, consistent pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic properties, fixed

oral dosing, rapid onset and offset of action.^[3, 10-12] In addition, they associated with less bleeding complications, and minimal drug and food interactions.^[13] On other hand, there are some issues should be considered. An example of this, the majority of clinicians lack a good experience on its proper use that make them less interested to switch to DOACs use. Furthermore, the average acquisition costs are higher than VKAs, which make the healthcare system prefers warfarin dispensing over the DOACs.^[14] The uses of DOACs in some clinical situations also are still in grey area due to lack of strong evidence from the subclinical and clinical trials. Therefore, this review will explore briefly the pharmacology of DOACs, efficacy and safety profile. It also will discuss laboratory-monitoring tests, and current reversal agents.

1. PHARMACOLOGICAL PROPERTIES

1.1 Mechanism of action

The DOACs act via two different mechanisms. The xabans group (apixaban, rivaroxaban, edoxaban, betrixaban) are direct factor Xa antagonists, which competitively and reversibly inhibit free and prothrombinase-bound factor Xa in a concentration-dependent manner.^[15, 16] Inhibition of factor Xa results in decreased thrombin generation. The dabigatran etexilate directly binds to activated thrombin (IIa), and prevents formation of fibrin by restricting thrombin from breaking fibrinogen.^[8, 17]

1.2 Pharmacokinetics

It studies four properties, namely absorption, distribution, metabolism and excretion of drug.

1.2.1 Oral direct factor II (thrombin) inhibitors

Dabigatran administered orally as a prodrug (dabigatran etixalate). The oral bioavailability is only 6.5% because of water solubility^[18,19] that is independent on drug dosing or presence of food.^[20] The time to reach peak plasma concentration (C_{max}) is 1-3hrs, which is not related to age and sex of patient.^[21] The volume of distribution (V_d) is approximately 60-70L with plasma protein binding is 35%. It converted to active form (dabigatran) primarily via the GIT esterase and not through CYP450 hepatic system.^[21] The primary route of elimination is through kidney.^[18, 21] The plasma concentration reaches steady state within 2-3 days with a half-life (T_{1/2}) of 12-18 hours^[22, 23] (see table.1).

1.2.2 Oral direct factor Xa inhibitors

Rivaroxaban absorbed rapidly after oral administration with a maximum plasma concentration (C_{max}) reached 2-4 hours.^[24, 25] It has an excellent oral bioavailability (80-100%).^[24] It undergoes oxidation and hydrolysis primarily via CYP3A4/5, CYP2J2 and CYP - independent mechanisms in liver, and a substrate of P-gp.^[26, 27] It excreted via the biliary/fecal (28%) and renal (66%) routes, with 36% of rivaroxaban excreted unchanged in the urine.^[28] It has a high plasma protein binding (90-95%) and V_d of 50L.^[27] The elimination half-life ranges from 5 to 9 hours in healthy subjects^[24, 25] and 11- 13hrs in elderly subjects^[29, 30] (see table.1).

Apixaban has a C_{max} occurring 3-4hours after oral administration.^[31,32] The oral bioavailability is

approximately 50% due to incomplete oral absorption and high first-pass effect via the gut and liver.^[33-36] The mean T_{1/2} is ~ 12 hr.^[31, 37, 38] The elimination of apixaban includes metabolism, biliary and renal excretion of unchanged parent drug as well as direct intestinal excretion.^[39,40] It undergoes O-demethylation, hydroxylation, and sulfation via CYP3A4, CYP1A2, 2C8, 2C9, 2C19, and 2J2 enzymes.^[35] It has a plasma protein binding of 93% in healthy subjects that is comparable to patients with end stage renal disease (ESRD) and hepatic impairment.^[41] Finally, the volume of distribution is only 21L, which indicates that the drug distributes in the extracellular fluid compartment^[33, 34, 42] as in (table.1).

Edoxaban has peak plasma concentrations of 1-2 hour following oral administration.^[43] It has an absolute oral bioavailability of 62%.^[44,45] Minority of drug undergoes biotransformation via hydrolysis, conjugation, and oxidation by CYP3A4. Edoxaban excreted via feces (60%), urine (35%) and over 70% of drug excreted unchanged with terminal half-life of 10-14 hour^[46] (see table.1). Finally, betrixaban has oral bioavailability of 34%, and oral absorption is decreased by presence of fatty meal.^[47,48] The peak plasma concentrations occur within 3-4 hours after oral administration.^[47] The primary route of elimination is hepatobiliary route of (82% to 89%) via P-glycoprotein (P-gp) efflux pumps and minority via renal route of (5-7%). Metabolism via hepatic cytochrome P450 enzymes represents only less than 1%.^[49, 50] The elimination half-life is from 19 to 27 hours^[51] with an apparent volume of distribution is 32 L/kg, and plasma protein binding of 60%.^[47, 52] (see table.1).

Table 1: Pharmacokinetic properties of the DOACs.

	Dabigatran	Rivaroxaban	Apixaban	Edoxaban	Betrixaban
Prodrug	Yes	No	No	No	No
Bioavailability	6.5%	80-100%	50%	62%	34%
Time to reach C_{max}.	1-3hrs	2-4hrs	3-4hrs	1-2hrs	3-4hrs
Food effect	Delay	Increase at dose 20mg	No	No	Decrease (fatty meal).
T_{1/2}	12-18 hr	5-9 hr	12 hr	10-14 hr	19-27 hr
V_d	60-70L	50L	21L	107L	32L/kg
Plasma protein binding	35%	90-95%	93%	55%	60%
Hepatic metabolism	None	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
CYP 450 subfamily	None	CYP3A4/5, CYP2J2	CYP3A4,CYP1A2, 2C8, 2C9, 2C19, 2J2	CYP3A4	CYP 1A1, 1A2, 2B6, 2C9, 2C19, 2D6, 3A4
Renal excretion	80%	66%	27%	35%	5-7%
Fecal excretion	82-88%	28%	46 -56%	60%	82-89%
Drug interactions	P-gp	CYP3A4/ P-gp	CYP3A4 / P-gp	P-gp	P-gp

V_d: volume of distribution, T_{1/2}: Half-life of drug, P-gp: Permeability-glycoprotein, C_{max}: Maximum plasma concentration.

1.3 Clinical uses, efficacy and safety profile

1.3.1 Stroke prophylaxis

Dabigatran, rivaroxaban, apixaban, and edoxaban were approved via the FDA to decrease risk of stroke and embolism in patients with non-valvular atrial fibrillation (NVAf).^[23, 30, 42, 48, 53-58] Compared with warfarin, a

meta-analysis of the phase III clinical trial data revealed that the NOACs are non-inferior for prevention of stroke and systemic embolism without increase risk of bleeding with similar reduction in cardiovascular mortality, and 10% reduction of all-cause of mortality.^[59, 60] Apixaban was compared with aspirin in 5559 patients with AF,

who were not candidate for warfarin use or unable to tolerate it. Apixaban was significantly decrease the annual rate of stroke or systemic embolism from 3.7% to 1.6% (hazard ratio: 0.45; 95% CI: 0.32– 0.62; $P < 0.001$) without a significant increase in the annual rate of major bleeding from 1.4% to 1.2%.^[61] Dabigatran administered at a dose of 110 mg or 150 mg and compared with warfarin in patients with AF. As a result, the rate of stroke and systemic embolism were similar and lower to those associated with warfarin at doses of 110 mg and 150 mg respectively and associated with lower rates of major hemorrhage for both different doses.^[62] Presence of valvular AF, which means presence of mechanical prosthetic heart valve or moderate to severe mitral stenosis increases thromboembolic risk that consider as an exclusion criterion from the DOACs phase III AF trials.^[63] Moreover, based on the RE-ALIGN trial (Dabigatran Versus Warfarin in Patients with Mechanical Heart Valves) conducted on 2011, the result was disappointed as dabigatran was associated with excess thromboembolic and bleeding events in patients with mechanical heart valves.^[64] Therefore, the warfarin was preferred over DOACs specifically in this group of patients similar to recommendations that made via the American College of Chest Physicians and American College of Cardiology/American Heart Association guidelines.^[65, 66] The bioprosthetic heart valves are less thrombogenic compared with mechanical heart valves. However, they are associated with increased risk and require chronic anticoagulation in setting of concurrent AF or mitral stenosis.^[67] The existing evidence to support the use of DOACs is limited. Thus, further studies and randomized controlled trials are needed to investigate the safety and efficacy of this class in this type of patients.^[68]

1.3.2 DVT and PE prophylaxis / treatment

Venous thromboembolism includes deep-vein thrombosis (DVT) and pulmonary embolism (PE). It is the third most common cause of vascular disease – related deaths.^[69,70] The mainstay of treatment is anticoagulation for 3 months or longer.^[71, 72] The current standard treatment is rapid acting parenteral anticoagulation for 5 to 7 days followed by oral anticoagulation e.g. warfarin, dabigatran or edoxaban for 3 months.^[73] This class was approved for treatment and prevention of recurrent DVT and PE.^[23, 30, 42, 74] A meta-analysis of phase III trials compared the NOACs with VKAs in patients with acute VTE suggested that the NOACs reduce the rates of recurrent VTE and VTE related mortality similar to warfarin with lower risk of major bleeding complications.^[75] According to the RE-COVER study (dabigatran versus warfarin in treatment of acute VTE) that conducted from 2006 to 2009, and included the RE-COVER I and II trials (primary outcome was 6-month incidence of recurrent symptomatic or fatal VTE). As a result, a fixed dose of dabigatran was as effective as warfarin, and did not require laboratory monitoring in treatment of acute VTE.^[76, 77]

1.3.3 Thromboprophylaxis

Patients, who underwent elective hip or knee arthroplasty require extended thromboprophylaxis as one of LMWHs e.g. fondaparinux, or adjusted-dose of vitamin K antagonist (VKA) e.g. warfarin for 10 days post-surgery.^[78] Apixaban and rivaroxaban were approved as prophylaxis of venous thromboembolism after total knee replacement (TKR) and total hip replacement (THR).^[30,42,79] Weili et al. (2015) stated that DOACs were effective to prevent venous thromboembolism after total hip or knee replacement. However; the bleeding rate was higher with rivaroxaban than apixaban and edoxaban use.^[80] Lassen et al. (2007) also demonstrated that apixaban at doses of 2.5 mg b.i.d. or 5 mg q.d. has a promising benefit–risk profile compared with current treatment after elective total knee arthroplasty.^[81] Moreover, Yong Bing et al. (2010) concluded that rivaroxaban was more effective than the recommended dose of enoxaparin with similar safety profile as thromboprophylaxis following TKR and THR.^[82] In addition, betrixaban was approved as prophylaxis of venous thromboembolism in hospitalized patients with acute medical illness, who at risk for thromboembolic complications due to moderate to severe restricted mobility and other risk factors for VTE.^[52, 83] The APEX study conducted from (2012-2015) compared betrixaban at dosing of 80 mg once a day orally for 35-42 days with the standard-duration of LMWHs e.g. enoxaparin at a dose of 40 mg once a day subcutaneous (S.C) for 6-14 days in hospitalized acute ill patients. The study demonstrated that extended prophylaxis with betrixaban resulted to a reduction in the VTE compared with standard short duration of enoxaparin in acute ill hospitalized patients with known risk factors for post discharge VTE.^[84] Samuel et al. (2011) and Michael et al. (2009) also have made similar finding, as an extended course of thromboprophylaxis with apixaban was similar to a shorter duration with enoxaparin. However, it was associated with significant bleeding events in acute ill patients.^[85, 86]

1.3.4 Acute coronary syndrome (ACS)

ACS usually triggered by thrombosis after rupture of atherosclerotic plaque in coronary artery. The anticoagulant therapy usually added to antiplatelet therapy to decrease the risk of recurrent ischemic attack. Improved cardiovascular outcomes were reported in patients, who were treated with warfarin and aspirin.^[87] Rivaroxaban has unique indication as the first DOAC licensed for this indication in combination with aspirin to reduce the risk of cardiovascular events in patients with coronary artery disease (CAD) or peripheral vascular disease.^[30] Jessica L et al. (2011) compared rivaroxaban at doses of 2.5 or 5 mg b.i.d with placebo in patients with stabilized ACS. As a result, rivaroxaban was significantly decrease the risk of cardiovascular death, myocardial infarction (MI) or stroke from 10.7% to 8.9% (hazard ratio: 0.84; 95% CI: 0.74 – 0.96; $P = 0.008$).^[88] In addition, compared with placebo, rivaroxaban increased the rates of major bleeding from 0.6% to 2.1%

($P < 0.001$) and intracranial hemorrhage from 0.2% to 0.6% ($P = 0.009$) without a significant increase in the rate of fatal bleeding from 0.2% to 0.3% ($P = 0.66$).^[88] John W et al. (2017) also stated that the combination of rivaroxaban at dosing of 2.5 mg twice a day and aspirin at dosing of 100 mg once a day had better cardiovascular outcomes and more major bleeding events compared with use of aspirin alone. Furthermore, rivaroxaban at a

dose of 5 mg twice a day had cardiovascular outcomes similar to use of aspirin alone. However, it was associated with more bleeding complications in patients with stable atherosclerotic vascular disease.^[89]

1.4 Drug dosing and dosage forms

The drug dosing, frequency, and dosage forms that related to clinical uses described in table. 2.^[23, 30, 42, 46, 52]

Table 2: Approved doses, dosages form and clinical indications of DOACs.

Class		NVAF	DVT & PE	Thromboprophylaxis	ACS
Dabigatran	Dose	75 - 150 mg ^(a)	150 mg	110 mg ^(b)	-----
	Frequency	b.i.d	b.i.d	q.d	-----
	Dosage form	Capsules			
Apixaban	Dose	5 mg ^(c)	10 mg, 2.5 mg ^(d)	2.5 mg	-----
	Frequency	b.i.d	b.i.d	b.i.d	-----
	Dosage form	Tablets			
Rivaroxaban	Dose	15 or 20 mg	15 mg	10 mg ^(e)	2.5 mg ^(f)
	Frequency	q.d	q.d	q.d	q.d
	Dosage form	Tablets			
Edoxaban	Dose	60 mg ^(g)	60 mg ^(h)	-----	-----
	Frequency	q.d	q.d	-----	-----
	Dosage form	Tablets			
Betrixaban	Dose	-----	-----	80 mg ⁽ⁱ⁾	-----
	Frequency	-----	-----	q.d	-----
	Dosage form	Capsules			

^(a) In patients with CrCl >30 mL/min is 150mg reduced to 75mg in patients with CrCl=15-30 mL/min. ^(b) In patients post HRT with CrCl >30 mL/min is 110mg 1st day, then 220 mg. ^(c) Patients with at least two of the following characteristics: age ≥ 80 years, body weight ≤ 60 kg, or serum creatinine ≥ 1.5 mg/dL, dose is 2.5 mg. ^(d) Reduction in the risk of recurrent following initial therapy. ^(e) Prophylaxis of VTE in acute ill medical patients start in hospital and after hospital discharge for 31 to 39 days. ^(f) Combined with aspirin 75-100 mg day. ^(g+h) It should not use in patients with CrCL > 95 mL/min, and reduce dose to 30 mg in patients with CrCL from 15 -50 mL/min or body weight ≤ 60 kg or who use P-gp inhibitors. ⁽ⁱ⁾ The recommended duration of treatment is 35 to 42 days and reduce dose for patients with severe renal impairment & (P-gp) inhibitors. q.d: once a day. b.i.d: twice a day.

1.5 Major drug interactions

Drug-drug interactions are a major concern for any clinician prescribe this class of medication. Concomitant administered drugs that alter DOAC plasma concentrations may lead to serious complications, either thromboembolism or bleeding. Even though, this class has minimal drug interactions compared to VKAs, which have significant drug interactions. The drug interactions comprise pharmacokinetic (PK) and pharmacodynamic (PD) interactions that classified according to underlying mechanism. The one of important pharmacokinetic drug interactions is the plasma protein binding. Rivaroxaban and apixaban are showing values above 90%. Thus, these two drugs may displaced by other drugs that have high

affinity to albumin and increased plasma concentrations of DOACs. Moreover, P-glycoprotein (P-gp) is an adenosine triphosphate (ATP)-dependent efflux transporter located in the plasma membranes of different cells and plays an important role in the PK profile of all DOACs by impairing their intestinal absorption, enhancing hepatic and renal elimination.^[90] Therefore, potent P-gp inhibitors or inducers expected to have relevant pharmacological interactions with all DOACs either increasing or reducing their anticoagulant effects. In addition, all DOACs eliminated by CYP metabolic enzymes e.g. CYP3A4 can contribute to major drug-drug interactions and place the patient at risk of complications.^[53] An example of this, CYP3A4 inhibitors with the use of apixaban, which has the highest reliance on hepatic biotransformation for clearance.^[42] Therefore, the dose of apixaban should be reduced by 50% when it is coadministered with drugs that are combined P-gp and strong CYP3A4 inhibitors, such as ketoconazole, itraconazole, and ritonavir.^[42] The presence of food also may affect DOACs absorption and plasma concentrations. Food slightly delays dabigatran absorption (C max from 2 hr to 4 hr), while oral bioavailability of rivaroxaban is significantly increased specifically at a dose of 20 mg.^[30, 91] The oral bioavailability of betrixaban is also affected by fatty meal, which reduces peak plasma concentration and the area under curve by 50%.^[47, 48, 83] In contrast, the bioavailability of apixaban and edoxaban are not influenced by the presence of food.^[32, 92, 93] The St. John's wort is one of the most remedies that commonly used for treatment of depression.^[94] The St. John's wort

acts as strong inducer of P-gp and CYP3A4, which can potentially affect the anticoagulant action of all DOACs.^[95] Therefore, the plasma concentration of all DOACs are expected to decrease and should be avoided in concomitant with the St. John's wort use.^[96] In an open-label, nonrandomized, sequential treatment interaction study conducted on 12 healthy volunteers, St. John's wort extract was significantly reduced extent of absorption and maximum plasma concentration of rivaroxaban by 24% and 14%, respectively.^[97] Therefore, clinicians should determine the plasma concentration of DOACs via using anti-fXa chromogenic assay.^[98]

On other hand, different classes of DOACs may have pharmacodynamic (PD) drug interactions by affecting platelets activation or coagulation pathway. For PD prospective analysis, results from four allocated RCTs have investigated efficacy and safety of DOACs or warfarin with P2Y12 receptor antagonists e.g. clopidogrel in patients with atrial fibrillation (AF) and ACS, who underwent percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI).^[99-101] These trials showed that dual therapy with DOACs and P2Y12 receptor antagonists had a lower risk of bleeding compared with triple therapy, namely warfarin, aspirin, and clopidogrel. The bleeding risk reduction was induced by receiving the DOACs instead of warfarin and aspirin.^[101] In addition, the clinical relevant two-folds increase in bleeding time has been observed with aspirin at doses of 100 mg and 325 mg respectively in combination with edoxaban.^[102] Antiplatelet drugs are either inhibitors (ticagrelor, naproxen) or substrates (clopidogrel, enoxaparin) of P-gp.^[103, 104] Edoxaban with or without concomitant use of clopidogrel and ticagrelor showed a similar relative efficacy and reduced bleeding compared to warfarin. Although, a significant increase of bleeding risk was anticipated with all DOACs when administered with antiplatelet drugs.^[100] Although, the PK drug interactions did not observe when clopidogrel was administered at a dose of 75 mg q.d and dabigatran at a dose of 150 mg b.i.d in healthy volunteers. The single loading dose of 300 mg or 600 mg clopidogrel has increased dabigatran AUC and C_{max} by 30–40%.^[105] Moreover, it is rational to anticipate the PD interactions between NSAIDs and DOACs combination with a significant increase in the bleeding risk. The incidence of major bleeding during NSAIDs and DOACs combination was equal to 6.5 per 100 patient-years compared to 2.2 per 100 patient-years during anticoagulant use only.^[106]

2. LABORATORY MONITORING TESTS

Because of consistent properties of this class, routine laboratory monitoring tests usually are not necessary. However, laboratory testing may be useful in specific situations, namely bleeding or thromboembolic event during treatment, drug overdose and measurement of patient compliance.^[106] They classified into two subgroups based on level of information required, such as qualitative tests, which provide a knowledge on the haemostasis state of patients e.g. prothrombin time (PT),

activated partial thromboplastin time (APTT) as well as thrombin time (TT).^[107] The quantitative tests are usually used to measure plasma drug concentrations e.g. liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (LC-MS), coagulometric and chromogenic assays for dabigatran, and chromogenic anti-FXa assays with drug-specific calibrators for inhibitors of FXa.^[107]

2.1 Liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (LC-MS)

It is the most reliable laboratory assay used to investigate the plasma level of drugs.^[108, 109] The LC-MS directly quantifies drug concentrations and does not require calibration via using a known concentration of the DOACs. The analytical range is between 5 and 500 ng/mL for all DOACs, which is sufficient to quantify peak and trough concentrations.^[110] It is highly specific, rapid and provides reliable and accurate results. However, it requires expensive equipment and well-trained people. Because of its complexity, only few highly specialized laboratories have this type of technology that can perform DOACs concentration measurement. Other assays can be used extensively in researches and clinical trials, and cannot be used routinely in clinical situations for rapid testing.^[111, 112]

2.2 Clot-based assays

These tests work by measuring the time needed for plasma-containing DOACs to form clot after adding calcium and activator. It includes prothrombin time (PT), activated partial thromboplastin time (APTT), and thrombin time (TT).^[113] These are screening tests, which can be used in cases of emergency to support clinical decision. However, it is insufficient to assess degree of anticoagulant effects. PT is used to assess the coagulation profile of rivaroxaban.^[114] The effects of edoxaban on PT seems stronger than betrixaban and rivaroxaban. Apixaban produces slight or no effect on PT.^[115] The anti-Xa DOACs sensitivity is insufficient at concentrations lower than or close to 30 ng/mL.^[108] By this way, PT can be useful to exclude high levels at trough concentration of rivaroxaban or edoxaban in plasma via using sensitive reagents. The APTT test estimates the intrinsic coagulation pathway function. It could be used to monitor dabigatran and screening test for the risk of overdose.^[116] It is slightly prolonged at the C_{max} of anti-FXa drugs with comparable anticoagulant effects of betrixaban and edoxaban followed by rivaroxaban and apixaban.^[115] Rivaroxaban has a higher sensitivity to APTT compared to other direct factor Xa inhibitors.^[117] Because of its sensitivity that depends on a reagent. It is generally insufficient to monitor treatment at the therapeutic concentrations^[109] (see table. 3).

Table 3: Effects of DOACs on the coagulation screening tests.

	PT / INR	APTT	TT
Dabigatran	Increase at Cmax	Increase	Increase at C trough
Rivaroxaban	Increase	Increase at Cmax	No change
Apixaban	Slight or no change	Slight or no change	No change
Edoxaban	Increase	Increase at Cmax	No change
Betrixiban	Increase	Increase at Cmax	No change

APTT: activated partial thromboplastin time; PT: prothrombin time; TT: thrombin time; INR: international normalized ratio.

2.3 Quantitative routine assays

They include the ecarin clotting time (ECT), chromogenic ecarin assay (CEA), chromogenic anti-FIIa assay, and diluted TT, which can be used to measure the plasma concentration of dabigatran.^[118-120] The ECT usually used to measure dabigatran concentration above therapeutic level, and depends on the time taken to form a clot. The CEA relies mainly on color generations. The ECT and ECA show a good correlation with LC-MS result.^[118, 121] The diluted thrombin time (TT) is a clotting test in which a patient plasma diluted with a buffer, mixed with normal plasma, and coagulation triggered by adding purified human thrombin. The diluted TT has a linear dose response relationship with clotting times, and inversely proportional to dabigatran plasma concentrations. In the chromogenic anti-FIIa method, thrombin incubated and diluted with a patient plasma. The residual thrombin hydrolyzes a thrombin-specific chromogenic substrate, releasing paranitroaniline (pNA). The amount of released pNA is measured by the optical density generated per minute, which is inversely proportional to concentration of dabigatran in the sample.^[4] The chromogenic anti-FXa assays have been used in clinical laboratories for several decades to monitor heparins, heparin-like therapies, and measure plasma concentrations of anti-Xa drugs.^[122]

3. REVERSAL AGENTS

In the last five years, there are new specific reversals, which approved via the FDA. Various approaches and interventions were utilized to reverse effects of the DOACs before approval of specific reversal agents. These approaches depend on the severity of bleeding. The success of such measures were largely depended on the timing of last anticoagulant dose, administrated dose, concurrent medications, site of bleeding, and patient comorbidities. The standard regimen was either delay or withhold the subsequent dosing in cases of mild to moderate bleeding.^[123] However, blood transfusion and mechanical compression were employed in sever bleeding situations.^[124, 125] They classified into nonspecific and specific agents. The nonspecific antidotes include prothrombin complex concentrate (PCC), fresh frozen plasma (FFP), recombinant activated factor VII (rFVIIa), activated PCC (aPCC), as well as hemodialysis for dabigatran overdose. The specific agents are idarucizumab, andexanet alfa, and ciraparantag, which used specifically to counteract dabigatran and factor Xa inhibitors in life-threatening bleeding.

3.1 Nonspecific reversals

All available data regarding efficacy of nonspecific reversal agents in the DOACs-associated bleeding are limited.^[126, 127]

3.1.1 Prothrombin complex concentrate (PCC)

It is a plasma-derived concentrate containing vitamin K-dependent clotting factors. One preparation contains three factors, namely factor II, IX, and X. Other contains four factors e.g. factor II, VII, IX, and X, as well as varied amounts of protein C and S.^[128] In three small randomized, placebo-controlled studies, the PCC reversed anticoagulant effects of rivaroxaban and edoxaban, and did not reverse dabigatran effects.^[126, 128, 129] In an open-label, parallel-group study compared efficacy of three-factor PCC with four-factor PCC formulations on prothrombin time (PT) of 35 healthy volunteers, who received rivaroxaban of 20 mg twice a day for 4 days followed by 50 unit/kg of three or four factor PCC intravenous infusion. The four-factor PCC reduced PT mean by 2.5-3.5 seconds, while three-factor PCC reduced the mean by 1-1.6 seconds.^[129] Therefore, the PCC can be used to reverse DOACs effects in patients with major bleeding. Similarly, a randomized crossover trial on 12 healthy volunteers, who received apixaban at a dose of 5 mg twice a day followed by four-factor PCC at a dose of 25unit/kg intravenous infusion for 3 hours after the last dose of apixaban.^[130] Thrombin generation increased by 76% at 30 minutes post four-factor PCC infusion. There were no differences in anti-Xa and activated partial thromboplastin time (APTT) values between four-factor PCC and placebo.^[130] Although, the data regarding efficacy for restoration of hemostasis was limited. The bleeding time reduced with PCC compared to placebo in the edoxaban-treated healthy volunteers, who were undergoing punch biopsy.^[131] In addition, the incidence of VTE was low and similar to that reported with the use of PCC for reversal VKAs.^[132] The contribution of an unmasked thrombotic process was attributed to anticoagulation cessation or activation of coagulation cascades by hemorrhage and should be considered.^[132] Adverse effects include thrombosis, and transmission of infections, which considered rare with new preparations.^[133]

3.1.2 Activated prothrombin complex concentrate (APCC)

APCC is anti-inhibitor coagulant complex that works as a factor VIII inhibitor bypassing activity (FEIBA).^[134] It

is a plasma-derived concentrate of factors II, VII, IX, and X that activated during manufacturing process. Firstly, it was developed to manage bleeding in patients with hemophilia A and B, who had inhibitors to factor VIII or IX. Recently, studies have demonstrated its usefulness as an off-label drug that can be used to reverse the anticoagulant effects of DOACs in patients with active bleeding.^[135] In a series of 127 patients, six patients developed spontaneous intracranial hemorrhage (ICH) secondary to DOACs use and managed with APCC at dosing of 50 unit/kg; none of these patients developed an ICH expansion, thrombotic or hemorrhagic complications.^[136] However, the thrombotic events were 4.05 per 105 infusions in hemophilic patients treated with APCC.^[140] In addition, APCC has been demonstrated to correct the PT and some thrombin generation indices in healthy subjects treated with rivaroxaban.^[137, 138]

3.1.3 Recombinant activated factor VII (rFVIIa)

The factor was primarily developed for treatment of bleeding in hemophilia patients, who had factor inhibitors. A dose of 90 µg/kg has been suggested to reverse major bleeding causing via the DOACs.^[127] Compared to placebo, the off-label use of rFVIIa was associated with an increased risk of arterial thromboembolic events.^[139]

3.1.4 Hemodialysis

Hemodialysis has been used to reverse dabigatran associated life-threatening bleeding.^[140] The main properties of this agent is a small plasma protein binding and has high renal clearance that makes it easy to dialyze. According to published literatures, a 4-hour hemodialysis session can reduce plasma concentrations up to 68% of dabigatran.^[141, 142] Even though, drug levels can increase after intermittent dialysis due to redistribution from extravascular compartments.^[143, 144] In contrast, factor X inhibitors are not dialyzable because of high plasma binding e.g. rivaroxaban and apixaban, and large volume of distribution, such as edoxaban, and betrixaban. In a study evaluated the pharmacokinetics and safety of edoxaban in patients, who underwent hemodialysis. Hemodialysis had only a minor decrease in the mean total exposure (AUC 0→∞ 676.2 ng h/ml) compared with patients off-dialysis (AUC 0→∞ 691.7 ng h/ml), suggesting that hemodialysis would not be an efficient way of drug removal in case of edoxaban overdose.^[145]

3.2 Specific reversals

3.2.1 Idarucizumab

A humanized monoclonal antibody fragment, which acts directly by binding to dabigatran to reverse its anticoagulant effects.^[146] It approved via the FDA on 2015. According to the 2019 update of the 2014 AHA/ACC/HRS guidelines for management of patients with atrial fibrillation recommended that the use of idarucizumab was to counteract dabigatran associated life-threatening bleeding or during urgent procedures.^[147]

It binds to free and thrombin-bound dabigatran and neutralizes its activity.^[148] Idarucizumab was available as a single-dose vial 2.5 g/50 ml solution for intravenous bolus and administered as two 50 ml intravenous boluses with 2.5 g each within 15 minutes.^[149] It excreted through the kidney, and had a half-life of 45 minutes.^[150] The potency has been tested in phase I and II clinical trials. Idarucizumab administration had no effect on the coagulation profile, indicating that it has no prothrombotic effects.^[151, 152] It normalized clotting times e.g. dilute thrombin time or ecarin clotting time in 88–98 % of patients within minutes and test results remained normal for the subsequent 24 hr. According to Chen Jin et al. (2018) stated that the rate of symptomatic intracranial hemorrhage among dabigatran treated patients and reversed with idarucizumab prior to administration of intravenous tissue-type plasminogen activator (tPA) was (4.5%) versus (7.4%) and mortality rate was (4.5%) versus (12.0%) compared with those who did not receive the reversal agents.^[153] The observations concluded that administration of idarucizumab before tPA was an emerging strategy that associated with more favorable outcomes.^[153]

3.2.2 Andexanet alfa

It is a genetically modified human factor Xa protein that binds and sequesters factor Xa inhibitors, namely rivaroxaban, edoxaban, apixaban, and betrixaban.^[154-156] It approved via the FDA since 2018. It had a half-life of 1 hour.^[156, 157] Andexanet alfa is available as a 100 mg vial for intravenous infusion, and recommended as a single intravenous bolus (400 or 800 mg) followed by a continuous intravenous infusion for up to 120 min (4 or 8 mg/min).^[158] Based on the ANNEXA-4 clinical trial conducted on 2020, which evaluated the efficacy of andexanet alfa to achieve hemostasis after major bleeding associated with rivaroxaban, apixaban, edoxaban, and enoxaparin use. There was a 92% reduction in the median of anti-factor Xa activity after andexanet alfa treatment in patients with acute major bleeding, who received apixaban, rivaroxaban, or edoxaban within 18 hours. This clinical trial also concluded that an adequate clinical hemostasis was in 85% of patients with gastrointestinal bleeding, and 80% of patients with intracranial bleeding within 12 hours of andexanet alfa administration.^[159] Andexanet alfa also resulted in rapid reversal anticoagulant effects of betrixaban in healthy volunteers.

3.2.3 Ciraparantag (Aripazine; PER977)

It is a synthetic water-soluble cationic molecule, which has been developed to form strong noncovalent hydrogen bond, and charge-charge interactions that binds to heparin, direct factor Xa inhibitors, and thrombin inhibitors.^[160] The pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic properties were studied in double blind placebo controlled trials.

CONCLUSION

The DOACs have revolutionized anticoagulant therapy, and becoming the main therapy for stroke prevention in patients with AF and thromboembolism treatment and prophylaxis. The list of new clinical uses is still expanding. Because of consistent pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic properties, and advent of rapid and safe specific reversal agents. Definitely, it can replace VKAs e.g. warfarin in the clinical setting. Moreover, some issues may affect the efficacy and safety endpoint when prescribing these agents, and this review has been addressed these issues.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Elsumdi HH has reviewed thoroughly the published articles that related to topic, wrote and revised this article. She also established the review idea and article structure.

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REFERENCES

- Nasiri A, AlQahtani A, Rayes NH, AlQahtani R, Alkharras R, Alghethber H. Direct oral anticoagulant: Review article. *Journal of Family Medicine and Primary Care*, 2022; 11(8): 4180-3.
- Byon W, Garonzik S, Boyd RA, Frost CE. Apixaban: A Clinical Pharmacokinetic and Pharmacodynamic Review. *Clin Pharmacokinet*, 2019; 58(10): 1265-79.
- DeWald TA, Becker RC. The pharmacology of novel oral anticoagulants. *J Thromb Thrombolysis*, 2014; 37(2): 217-33.
- Dunois C. Laboratory Monitoring of Direct Oral Anticoagulants (DOACs). *Biomedicines*, 2021; 9(5): 4455.
- Aronis KN, Hylek EM. Evidence Gaps in the Era of Non-Vitamin K Oral Anticoagulants. *J Am Heart Assoc*, 2018; 7(3): e007338.
- Paul C, Baby M, Anthraper AR, K K. NOACs: an emerging class of oral anticoagulants-a review article. *Future Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 2020; 6(1): 957.
- Lancy Morries NM, Joel Joby Joseph, Suja Abraham. Newer Oral Anticoagulant Therapy – Prospects and Practices: A Review. *Indian Journal of Pharmacy Practice*, 2020; 13(3): 215-21.
- Yeh CH, Hogg K, Weitz JI. Overview of the New Oral Anticoagulants opportunities and challenges. *Arteriosclerosis, Thrombosis, and Vascular Biology*, 2015; 35(5): 1056-65.
- Harder S, Graff J. Novel oral anticoagulants: clinical pharmacology, indications and practical considerations. *Eur J Clin Pharmacol*, 2013; 69(9): 1617-33.
- Bauer KA. Pros and cons of new oral anticoagulants. *Hematology*, 2013; 2013(1): 464-70.
- Chen A, Stecker E, Warden BA. Direct Oral Anticoagulant Use: A Practical Guide to Common Clinical Challenges. *J Am Heart Assoc*, 2020; 9(13): e017559.
- Rose DK, Bar B. Direct Oral Anticoagulant Agents: Pharmacologic Profile, Indications, Coagulation Monitoring, and Reversal Agents. *J Stroke Cerebrovasc Dis*, 2018; 27(8): 2049-58.
- Mekaj YH, Mekaj AY, Duci SB, Miftari EI. New oral anticoagulants: their advantages and disadvantages compared with vitamin K antagonists in the prevention and treatment of patients with thromboembolic events. *Thromb Clin Risk Manag*, 2015; 11: 967-77.
- Yeh CH, Hogg K, Weitz JI. Overview of the new oral anticoagulants: opportunities and challenges. *Arteriosclerosis, Thrombosis, and Vascular Biology*, 2015; 35(5): 1056-65.
- Perzborn E, Strassburger J, Wilmen A, Pohlmann J, Roehrig S, Schlemmer KH, et al. In vitro and in vivo studies of the novel antithrombotic agent BAY 59-7939--an oral, direct Factor Xa inhibitor. *J Thromb Haemost*, 2005; 3(3): 514-21.
- Pinto DJ, Orwat MJ, Koch S, Rossi KA, Alexander RS, Smallwood A, et al. Discovery of 1-(4-methoxyphenyl)-7-oxo-6-(4-(2-oxopiperidin-1-yl)phenyl)-4,5,6,7-tetrahydro-1H-pyrazolo[3,4-c]pyridine-3-carboxamide (apixaban, BMS-562247), a highly potent, selective, efficacious, and orally bioavailable inhibitor of blood coagulation factor Xa. *J Med Chem.*, 2007; 50(22): 5339-56.
- Salem JE, Sabouret P, Funck-Brentano C, Hulot JS. Pharmacology and mechanisms of action of new oral anticoagulants. *Fundam Clin Pharmacol*, 2015; 29(1): 10-20.
- da Silva RM. Novel oral anticoagulants in non-valvular atrial fibrillation. *Cardiovasc Hematol Agents Med Chem.*, 2014; 12(1): 3-8.
- Stangier J, Rathgen K, Stähle H, Gansser D, Roth W. The pharmacokinetics, pharmacodynamics and tolerability of dabigatran etexilate, a new oral direct thrombin inhibitor, in healthy male subjects. *British Journal of Clinical Pharmacology*, 2007; 64(3): 292-303.
- Eriksson BI, Dahl OE, Büller HR, Hettiarachchi R, Rosencher N, Bravo ML, et al. A new oral direct thrombin inhibitor, dabigatran etexilate, compared with enoxaparin for prevention of thromboembolic events following total hip or knee replacement: the BISTRO II randomized trial. *J Thromb Haemost.*, 2005; 3(1): 103-11.
- Blech S, Ebner T, Ludwig-Schwellinger E, Stangier J, Roth W. The Metabolism and Disposition of the Oral Direct Thrombin Inhibitor, Dabigatran, in Humans. *Drug Metabolism and Disposition*, 2008; 36(2): 386.
- Stangier J, Stähle H, Rathgen K, Fuhr R. Pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics of the

- direct oral thrombin inhibitor dabigatran in healthy elderly subjects. *Clin Pharmacokinet*, 2008; 47(1): 47-59.
23. BoehringerIngelheimPharmaceuticals. PRADAXA® (dabigatran etexilate). 2010; Available from: www.pradaxa.com.
 24. Kubitz D, Becka M, Wensing G, Voith B, Zuehlsdorf M. Safety, pharmacodynamics, and pharmacokinetics of BAY 59-7939--an oral, direct Factor Xa inhibitor--after multiple dosing in healthy male subjects. *Eur J Clin Pharmacol*. 2005; 61(12): 873-80.
 25. Kubitz D, Becka M, Voith B, Zuehlsdorf M, Wensing G. Safety, pharmacodynamics, and pharmacokinetics of single doses of BAY 59-7939, an oral, direct factor Xa inhibitor. *Clin Pharmacol Ther.*, 2005; 78(4): 412-21.
 26. De Caterina R, Husted S, Wallentin L, Andreotti F, Arnesen H, Bachmann F, et al. New oral anticoagulants in atrial fibrillation and acute coronary syndromes: ESC Working Group on Thrombosis-Task Force on Anticoagulants in Heart Disease position paper. *J Am Coll Cardiol.*, 2012; 59(16): 1413-25.
 27. Mueck W, Stampfuss J, Kubitz D, Becka M. Clinical pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic profile of rivaroxaban. *Clin Pharmacokinet*, 2014; 53(1): 1-16.
 28. Turpie AG. Oral, direct factor Xa inhibitors in development for the prevention and treatment of thromboembolic diseases. *Arteriosclerosis, Thrombosis, and Vascular Biology*, 2007; 27(6): 1238-47.
 29. Kubitz D, Becka M, Roth A, Mueck W. Dose-escalation study of the pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics of rivaroxaban in healthy elderly subjects. *Curr Med Res Opin.*, 2008; 24(10): 2757-65.
 30. Pharmaceuticals J. XARELTO® (rivaroxaban). 2011 [18/06/2023]; Available from: www.janssenpatents.com.
 31. Frost C, Nepal S, Wang J, Schuster A, Byon W, Boyd RA, et al. Safety, pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics of multiple oral doses of apixaban, a factor Xa inhibitor, in healthy subjects. *British Journal of Clinical Pharmacology*, 2013; 76(5): 776-86.
 32. Frost C, Wang J, Nepal S, Schuster A, Barrett YC, Mosqueda-Garcia R, et al. Apixaban, an oral, direct factor Xa inhibitor: single dose safety, pharmacokinetics, pharmacodynamics and food effect in healthy subjects. *British Journal of Clinical Pharmacology*. 2013; 75(2): 476-87.
 33. Vakkalagadda B, Frost C, Byon W, Boyd RA, Wang J, Zhang D, et al. Effect of Rifampin on the Pharmacokinetics of Apixaban, an Oral Direct Inhibitor of Factor Xa. *Am J Cardiovasc Drugs*. 2016; 16(2): 119-27.
 34. Frost C. Apixaban, a direct factor Xa inhibitor : single-dose pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics of an intravenous formulation. *J Clin Pharmacol*. 2008; 48: 1132.
 35. Wang L, Zhang D, Raghavan N, Yao M, Ma L, Frost CE, et al. In vitro assessment of metabolic drug-drug interaction potential of apixaban through cytochrome P450 phenotyping, inhibition, and induction studies. *Drug Metab Dispos*. 2010; 38(3): 448-58.
 36. Zhang D, He K, Herbst JJ, Kolb J, Shou W, Wang L, et al. Characterization of efflux transporters involved in distribution and disposition of apixaban. *Drug Metab Dispos*. 2013; 41(4): 827-35.
 37. Frost C, Shenker A, Jhee S, Yu Z, Wang J, Bragat A, et al. Evaluation of the single-dose pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics of apixaban in healthy Japanese and Caucasian subjects. *Clin Pharmacol*, 2018; 10: 163-53.
 38. Yamahira N, Frost C, Fukase H, Yu Z, Wang J, Pursley J, et al. Safety, tolerability, pharmacokinetics, and pharmacodynamics of multiple doses of apixaban in healthy Japanese male subjects. *Int J Clin Pharmacol Ther*. 2014; 52(7): 564-73.
 39. Zhang D, He K, Raghavan N, Wang L, Mitroka J, Maxwell BD, et al. Comparative metabolism of ¹⁴C-labeled apixaban in mice, rats, rabbits, dogs, and humans. *Drug Metab Dispos*. 2009; 37(8): 1738-48.
 40. Wang X, Mondal S, Wang J, Tirucherai G, Zhang D, Boyd RA, et al. Effect of activated charcoal on apixaban pharmacokinetics in healthy subjects. *Am J Cardiovasc Drugs*. 2014; 14(2): 147-54.
 41. Wang X, Tirucherai G, Marbury TC, Wang J, Chang M, Zhang D, et al. Pharmacokinetics, pharmacodynamics, and safety of apixaban in subjects with end-stage renal disease on hemodialysis. *J Clin Pharmacol*. 2016; 56(5): 628-36.
 42. Company B-MSP. Eliquis (apixaban). 2012 [18/06/2023]; Available from: <http://www.ELIQUIS.com>.
 43. Stacy ZA, Call WB, Hartmann AP, Peters GL, Richter SK. Edoxaban: A Comprehensive Review of the Pharmacology and Clinical Data for the Management of Atrial Fibrillation and Venous Thromboembolism. *Cardiol Ther*. 2016; 5(1): 1-18.
 44. Matsushima N, Lee F, Sato T, Weiss D, Mendell J. Bioavailability and Safety of the Factor Xa Inhibitor Edoxaban and the Effects of Quinidine in Healthy Subjects. *Clinical Pharmacology in Drug Development*. 2013; 2(4): 358-66.
 45. Lip GYH, Agnelli G. Edoxaban: a focused review of its clinical pharmacology. *Eur Heart J*. 2014; 35(28): 18.55-44
 46. DaiichiSankyoCo. SAVAYSA (edoxaban). 2015; Available from: <https://savaysa.com>.
 47. Baker DE. Formulary Drug Review: Betrixaban. *Hosp Pharm*. 2018; 53(1): 29-37. Epub 2017/11/06.
 48. Chan NC, Bhagirath V, Eikelboom JW. Profile of betrixaban and its potential in the prevention and

- treatment of venous thromboembolism. *Vasc Health Risk Manag*. 2015; 11: 343-51.
49. Chan NC, Hirsh J, Ginsberg JS, Eikelboom JW. Betrixaban (PRT054021): pharmacology, dose selection and clinical studies. *Future Cardiol*. 2014; 1(10): 52-43.
 50. Hutchaleelaha A, Ye C, Song Y, Lorenz T, Gretler D, Lambing JL. Metabolism and Disposition of Betrixaban and Its Lack of Interaction with Major CYP Enzymes. *Blood*. 2012; 120(21): 2266.
 51. Palladino M, Merli G, Thomson L. Evaluation of the oral direct factor Xa inhibitor - betrixaban. *Expert Opin Investig Drugs*. 2013; 22(11): 1465-72.
 52. PortolaPharmaceuticals. BEVYXXA® (betrixaban. 2017; Available from: https://www.accessdata.fda.gov/drugsatfda_docs/label/2017/208383s000lbl.pdf.
 53. Chen A, Stecker E, B AW. Direct Oral Anticoagulant Use: A Practical Guide to Common Clinical Challenges. *J Am Heart Assoc*. 2020; 9(13): e017559.
 54. Connolly SJ, Ezekowitz MD, Yusuf S, Eikelboom J, Oldgren J, Parekh A, et al. Dabigatran versus warfarin in patients with atrial fibrillation. *N Engl J Med*. 2009; 361(12): 1139-51.
 55. Giugliano RP, Ruff CT, Braunwald E, Murphy SA, Wiviott SD, Halperin JL, et al. Edoxaban versus warfarin in patients with atrial fibrillation. *N Engl J Med*. 2013; 369(22): 2093-104.
 56. Granger CB, Alexander JH, McMurray JJ, Lopes RD, Hylek EM, Hanna M, et al. Apixaban versus warfarin in patients with atrial fibrillation. *N Engl J Med*. 2011; 365(11): 981-92.
 57. Patel MR, Mahaffey KW, Garg J, Pan G, Singer DE, Hacke W, et al. Rivaroxaban versus warfarin in nonvalvular atrial fibrillation. *N Engl J Med*. 2011; 365(10): 883-91.
 58. Rutherford OW, Jonasson C, Ghanima W, Söderdahl F, Halvorsen S. Comparison of dabigatran, rivaroxaban, and apixaban for effectiveness and safety in atrial fibrillation: a nationwide cohort study. *Eur Heart J Cardiovasc Pharmacother*. 2020; 6(2): 75-85.
 59. Ruff CT, Giugliano RP, Braunwald E, Hoffman EB, Deenadayalu N, Ezekowitz MD, et al. Comparison of the efficacy and safety of new oral anticoagulants with warfarin in patients with atrial fibrillation: a meta-analysis of randomised trials. *Lancet*. 2014; 383(9921): 955-62.
 60. Dong S-J, Luo C-Y, Xiao C-L, Zhang F-Z, Li L, Han Z-L, et al. Efficacy and Safety Profile of Novel Oral Anticoagulants in the Treatment of Left Atrial Thrombosis: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Current Therapeutic Research*. 2022; 96: 100670.
 61. Connolly SJ, Eikelboom J, Joyner C, Diener HC, Hart R, Golitsyn S, et al. Apixaban in patients with atrial fibrillation. *N Engl J Med*. 2011; 364(9): 806-17.
 62. Connolly SJ, Ezekowitz MD, Yusuf S, Eikelboom J, Oldgren J, Parekh A, et al. Dabigatran versus Warfarin in Patients with Atrial Fibrillation. *New England Journal of Medicine*. 2009; 361(12): 1139-51.
 63. Heidenreich PA, Estes NAM, 3rd, Fonarow GC, Jurgens CY, Kittleson MM, Marine JE, et al. 2020 Update to the 2016 ACC/AHA Clinical Performance and Quality Measures for Adults With Atrial Fibrillation or Atrial Flutter: A Report of the American College of Cardiology/American Heart Association Task Force on Performance Measures. *Circ Cardiovasc Qual Outcomes*. 2021; 14(1): e000100.
 64. Eikelboom JW, Connolly SJ, Brueckmann M, Granger CB, Kappetein AP, Mack MJ, et al. Dabigatran versus warfarin in patients with mechanical heart valves. *N Engl J Med*. 2013; 369(13): 14-1206.
 65. Whitlock RP, Sun JC, Fremes SE, Rubens FD, Teoh KH. Antithrombotic and thrombolytic therapy for valvular disease: Antithrombotic Therapy and Prevention of Thrombosis, 9th ed: American College of Chest Physicians Evidence-Based Clinical Practice Guidelines. *Chest*. 2012; 141(2 Suppl): e576S-e600S.
 66. January CT, Wann LS, Calkins H, Chen LY, Cigarroa JE, Cleveland JC, Jr., et al. 2019 AHA/ACC/HRS Focused Update of the 2014 AHA/ACC/HRS Guideline for the Management of Patients With Atrial Fibrillation: A Report of the American College of Cardiology/American Heart Association Task Force on Clinical Practice Guidelines and the Heart Rhythm Society in Collaboration With the Society of Thoracic Surgeons. *Circulation*. 2019; 140(2): e125-e51.
 67. Nishimura RA, Otto CM, Bonow RO, Carabello BA, Erwin JP, 3rd, Fleisher LA, et al. 2017 AHA/ACC Focused Update of the 2014 AHA/ACC Guideline for the Management of Patients With Valvular Heart Disease: A Report of the American College of Cardiology/American Heart Association Task Force on Clinical Practice Guidelines. *Circulation*. 2017; 135(25): e1159-e95.
 68. Bakr L, Elsayed A, Saleh O, Abdalraouf M, Ng GA, Ibrahim M. Safety and efficacy of direct oral anticoagulants in bioprosthetic valves: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Frontiers in Cardiovascular Medicine*. 2023; 10.
 69. Goldhaber SZ, Bounameaux H. Pulmonary embolism and deep vein thrombosis. *The Lancet*. 2012; 379(9828): 1835-46.
 70. Spencer FA, Emery C, Lessard D, Anderson F, Emani S, Aragam J, et al. The Worcester Venous Thromboembolism Study: A Population-Based Study of the Clinical Epidemiology of Venous Thromboembolism. *Journal of General Internal Medicine*. 2006; 21(7): 722-7.
 71. Kearon C, Akl EA, Comerota AJ, Prandoni P, Bounameaux H, Goldhaber SZ, et al.

- Antithrombotic therapy for VTE disease: Antithrombotic Therapy and Prevention of Thrombosis, 9th ed: American College of Chest Physicians Evidence-Based Clinical Practice Guidelines. *Chest*. 2012; 141(2 Suppl): e419S-e96S.
72. Torbicki A, Perrier A, Konstantinides S, Agnelli G, Galiè N, Pruszczyk P, et al. Guidelines on the diagnosis and management of acute pulmonary embolism: the Task Force for the Diagnosis and Management of Acute Pulmonary Embolism of the European Society of Cardiology (ESC). *Eur Heart J*. 2008; 29(18): 2276-315.
 73. Kearon C, Kahn SR, Agnelli G, Goldhaber S, Raskob GE, Comerota AJ. Antithrombotic Therapy for Venous Thromboembolic Disease: American College of Chest Physicians Evidence-Based Clinical Practice Guidelines (8th Edition). *Chest*. 2008; 133(6, Supplement): 454S-545S.
 74. Skelley JW, Thomason AR, Nolen JC, Candidate P. Betrixaban (Bevyxxa): A Direct-Acting Oral Anticoagulant Factor Xa Inhibitor. *P T*. 2018; 43(2): 85-120.
 75. van der Hulle T, Kooiman J, den Exter PL, Dekkers OM, Klok FA, Huisman MV. Effectiveness and safety of novel oral anticoagulants as compared with vitamin K antagonists in the treatment of acute symptomatic venous thromboembolism: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *J Thromb Haemost*. 2014; 12(3): 320-8.
 76. Schulman S, Kearon C, Kakkar AK, Mismetti P, Schellong S, Eriksson H, et al. Dabigatran versus Warfarin in the Treatment of Acute Venous Thromboembolism. *New England Journal of Medicine*. 2009; 361(24): 2342-52.
 77. Schulman S, Kakkar AK, Goldhaber SZ, Schellong S, Eriksson H, Mismetti P, et al. Treatment of Acute Venous Thromboembolism With Dabigatran or Warfarin and Pooled Analysis. *Circulation*. 2014; 129(7): 764-72.
 78. Geerts WH, Pineo GF, Heit JA, Bergqvist D, Lassen MR, Colwell CW, et al. Prevention of venous thromboembolism: the Seventh ACCP Conference on Antithrombotic and Thrombolytic Therapy. *Chest*. 2004; 126(3 Suppl): 338S-400S.
 79. Jiménez D, Yusen RD, Ramacciotti E. Apixaban: an oral direct factor-xa inhibitor. *Adv Ther*. 2012; 29(3): 187-201.
 80. Feng W, Wu K, Liu Z, Kong G, Deng Z, Chen S, et al. Oral direct factor Xa inhibitor versus enoxaparin for thromboprophylaxis after hip or knee arthroplasty: Systemic review, traditional meta-analysis, dose-response meta-analysis and network meta-analysis. *Thromb Res*. 2015; 136(6): 1133-44.
 81. LASSEN MR, DAVIDSON BL, GALLUS A, PINEO G, ANSELL J, DEITCHMAN D. The efficacy and safety of apixaban, an oral, direct factor Xa inhibitor, as thromboprophylaxis in patients following total knee replacement. *Journal of Thrombosis and Haemostasis*. 2007; 5(12): 2368-75.
 82. Cao YB, Zhang JD, Shen H, Jiang YY. Rivaroxaban versus enoxaparin for thromboprophylaxis after total hip or knee arthroplasty: a meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *Eur J Clin Pharmacol*. 2010; 66(11): 108-1099.
 83. Huisman MV, Klok FA. Pharmacological properties of betrixaban. *Eur Heart J Suppl*. 2018; 20(Suppl E): E12-E5. Epub 2018/05/09.
 84. Cohen AT, Harrington R, Goldhaber SZ, Hull R, Gibson CM, Hernandez AF, et al. The design and rationale for the Acute Medically Ill Venous Thromboembolism Prevention with Extended Duration Betrixaban (APEX) study. *Am Heart J*. 2014; 167(3): 335-41.
 85. Goldhaber SZ, Leizorovicz A, Kakkar AK, Haas SK, Merli G, Knabb RM, et al. Apixaban versus enoxaparin for thromboprophylaxis in medically ill patients. *N Engl J Med*. 2011; 365(23): 2167-77.
 86. Lassen MR, Raskob GE, Gallus A, Pineo G, Chen D, Portman RJ. Apixaban or enoxaparin for thromboprophylaxis after knee replacement. *N Engl J Med*. 2009; 361(6): 594-604.
 87. Warfarin plus Aspirin after Myocardial Infarction or the Acute Coronary Syndrome: Meta-Analysis with Estimates of Risk and Benefit. *Annals of Internal Medicine*. 2005; 143(4): 241-50.
 88. Mega JL, Braunwald E, Wiviott SD, Bassand J-P, Bhatt DL, Bode C, et al. Rivaroxaban in Patients with a Recent Acute Coronary Syndrome. *New England Journal of Medicine*. 2011; 366(1): 9-19.
 89. Eikelboom JW, Connolly SJ, Bosch J, Dagenais GR, Hart RG, Shestakovska O, et al. Rivaroxaban with or without Aspirin in Stable Cardiovascular Disease. *New England Journal of Medicine*. 2017; 377(14): 1319-30.
 90. Wolking S, Schaeffeler E, Lerche H, Schwab M, Nies AT. Impact of Genetic Polymorphisms of ABCB1 (MDR1, P-Glycoprotein) on Drug Disposition and Potential Clinical Implications: Update of the Literature. *Clin Pharmacokinet*. 2015; 54(7): 709-35.
 91. Stampfuss J, Kubitzka D, Becka M, Mueck W. The effect of food on the absorption and pharmacokinetics of rivaroxaban. *Int J Clin Pharmacol Ther*. 2013; 51(7): 549-61.
 92. Mendell J, Noveck RJ, Shi M. Pharmacokinetics of the direct factor Xa inhibitor edoxaban and digoxin administered alone and in combination. *J Cardiovasc Pharmacol*. 2012; 60(4): 335-41.
 93. Frost C, Garonzik S, Shenker A, Barrett YC, LaCreta F. Apixaban Single-Dose Pharmacokinetics, Bioavailability, Renal Clearance, and Pharmacodynamics Following Intravenous and Oral Administration. *Clinical Pharmacology in Drug Development*. 2021; 10(9): 974-84.
 94. Di YM, Li CG, Xue CC, Zhou SF. Clinical drugs that interact with St. John's wort and implication in drug development. *Curr Pharm Des*. 2008; 14(17): 1723-42.

95. Ruschitzka F, Meier PJ, Turina M, Lüscher TF, Noll G. Acute heart transplant rejection due to Saint John's wort. *Lancet*. 2000; 355(9203): 548-9.
96. Di Minno A, Frigerio B, Spadarella G, Ravani A, Sansaro D, Amato M, et al. Old and new oral anticoagulants: Food, herbal medicines and drug interactions. *Blood Rev*. 2017; 31(4): 193-203.
97. Scholz I, Liakoni E, Hammann F, Grafinger KE, Duthaler U, Nagler M, et al. Effects of Hypericum perforatum (St John's wort) on the pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics of rivaroxaban in humans. *British Journal of Clinical Pharmacology*. 2021; 87(3): 1466-74.
98. Steffel J, Collins R, Antz M, Cornu P, Desteghe L, Haeusler KG, et al. 2021 European Heart Rhythm Association Practical Guide on the Use of Non-Vitamin K Antagonist Oral Anticoagulants in Patients with Atrial Fibrillation. *Europace*. 2021; 23(10): 1612-76.
99. Vranckx P, Valgimigli M, Eckardt L, Tijssen J, Lewalter T, Gargiulo G, et al. Edoxaban-based versus vitamin K antagonist-based antithrombotic regimen after successful coronary stenting in patients with atrial fibrillation (ENTRUST-AF PCI): a randomised, open-label, phase 3b trial. *Lancet*. 2019; 394(10206): 1335-43.
100. Cannon CP, Bhatt DL, Oldgren J, Lip GYH, Ellis SG, Kimura T, et al. Dual Antithrombotic Therapy with Dabigatran after PCI in Atrial Fibrillation. *N Engl J Med*. 2017; 377(16): 1513-24.
101. Lopes RD, Heizer G, Aronson R, Vora AN, Massaro T, Mehran R, et al. Antithrombotic Therapy after Acute Coronary Syndrome or PCI in Atrial Fibrillation. *N Engl J Med*. 2019; 380(16): 1509-24.
102. Mendell J, Lee F, Chen S, Worland V, Shi M, Samama MM. The effects of the antiplatelet agents, aspirin and naproxen, on pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics of the anticoagulant edoxaban, a direct factor Xa inhibitor. *J Cardiovasc Pharmacol*. 2013; 62(2): 212-21.
103. Oh J, Shin D, Lim KS, Lee S, Jung KH, Chu K, et al. Aspirin decreases systemic exposure to clopidogrel through modulation of P-glycoprotein but does not alter its antithrombotic activity. *Clin Pharmacol Ther*. 2014; 95(6): 608-16.
104. Wessler JD, Grip LT, Mendell J, Giugliano RP. The P-glycoprotein transport system and cardiovascular drugs. *J Am Coll Cardiol*. 2013; 61(25): 2495-502.
105. Härtter S, Sennewald R, Schepers C, Baumann S, Fritsch H, Friedman J. Pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic effects of comedication of clopidogrel and dabigatran etexilate in healthy male volunteers. *Eur J Clin Pharmacol*. 2013; 69(3): 327-39.
106. Salmonson T, Dogné JM, Janssen H, Garcia Burgos J, Blake P. Non-vitamin-K oral anticoagulants and laboratory testing: now and in the future: Views from a workshop at the European Medicines Agency (EMA). *Eur Heart J Cardiovasc Pharmacother*. 2017; 3(1): 42-7.
107. Margetić S, Goreta S, Čelap I, Razum M. Direct oral anticoagulants (DOACs): From the laboratory point of view. *Acta Pharm*. 2022; 72(4): 459-82.
108. Gosselin RC, Adcock DM, Bates SM, Douxfils J, Favaloro EJ, Guoin-Thibault I, et al. International Council for Standardization in Haematology (ICSH) Recommendations for Laboratory Measurement of Direct Oral Anticoagulants. *Thromb Haemost*. 2018; 118(3): 437-50.
109. Cuker A, Siegal DM, Crowther MA, Garcia DA. Laboratory measurement of the anticoagulant activity of the non-vitamin K oral anticoagulants. *J Am Coll Cardiol*. 2014; 64(11): 1128-39.
110. Lange U, Nowak G, Bucha E. Ecarin chromogenic assay--a new method for quantitative determination of direct thrombin inhibitors like hirudin. *Pathophysiol Haemost Thromb*. 2003; 33(4): 184-91.
111. Schmohl M, Gansser D, Moschetti V, Stangier J. Measurement of dabigatran plasma concentrations by calibrated thrombin clotting time in comparison to LC-MS/MS in human volunteers on dialysis. *Thromb Res*. 2015; 135(3): 532-6.
112. Rohde G. Determination of rivaroxaban--a novel, oral, direct Factor Xa inhibitor--in human plasma by high-performance liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry. *J Chromatogr B Analyt Technol Biomed Life Sci*. 2008; 872(1-2): 43-50.
113. Lindhoff-Last E, Samama MM, Ortel TL, Weitz JI, Spiro TE. Assays for measuring rivaroxaban: their suitability and limitations. *Ther Drug Monit*. 2010; 32(6): 673-9.
114. Kitchen S, Gray E, Mackie I, Baglin T, Makris M. Measurement of non-coumarin anticoagulants and their effects on tests of Haemostasis: Guidance from the British Committee for Standards in Haematology. *Br J Haematol*. 2014; 166(6): 830-41.
115. Siddiqui F, Hoppensteadt D, Jeske W, Iqbal O, Tafur A, Fared J. Factor Xa Inhibitory Profile of Apixaban, Betrixaban, Edoxaban, and Rivaroxaban Does Not Fully Reflect Their Biologic Spectrum. *Clin Appl Thromb Hemost*. 2019; 25: 1076029619847524.
116. Douxfils J, Mullier F, Robert S, Chatelain C, Chatelain B, Dogné JM. Impact of dabigatran on a large panel of routine or specific coagulation assays. Laboratory recommendations for monitoring of dabigatran etexilate. *Thromb Haemost*. 2012; 107(5): 985-97.
117. Barrett YC, Wang Z, Frost C, Shenker A. Clinical laboratory measurement of direct factor Xa inhibitors: anti-Xa assay is preferable to prothrombin time assay. *Thromb Haemost*. 2010; 104(6): 1263-71.
118. Gosselin R, Hawes E, Moll S, Adcock D. Performance of Various Laboratory Assays in the Measurement of Dabigatran in Patients Receiving Therapeutic Doses: A Prospective Study Based on Peak and Trough Plasma Levels. *Am J Clin Pathol*. 2014; 141(2): 262-7.

119. Avecilla ST, Ferrell C, Chandler WL, Reyes M. Plasma-Diluted Thrombin Time to Measure Dabigatran Concentrations During Dabigatran Etxilate Therapy. *Am J Clin Pathol.* 2012; 137(4): 572-4.
120. Helin TA, Lemponen M, Hjemdahl P, Rönquist-Nii Y, Lassila R, Joutsu-Korhonen L. From laboratory to clinical practice: Dabigatran effects on thrombin generation and coagulation in patient samples. *Thromb Res.* 2015; 136(1): 154-60.
121. Gosselin R, Hawes E, Moll S, Adcock D. Performance of various laboratory assays in the measurement of dabigatran in patients receiving therapeutic doses: a prospective study based on peak and trough plasma levels. *Am J Clin Pathol.* 2014; 141(2): 262-7.
122. Samama MM, Amiral J, Guinet C, Perzborn E, Depasse F. An optimised, rapid chromogenic assay, specific for measuring direct factor Xa inhibitors (rivaroxaban) in plasma. *Thromb Haemost.* 2010; 104(5): 1078-9.
123. Steiner T, Böhm M, Dichgans M, Diener HC, Eil C, Endres M, et al. Recommendations for the emergency management of complications associated with the new direct oral anticoagulants (DOACs), apixaban, dabigatran and rivaroxaban. *Clin Res Cardiol.* 2013; 102(6): 399-412.
124. Christos S, Naples R. Anticoagulation Reversal and Treatment Strategies in Major Bleeding: Update 2016. *West J Emerg Med.* 2016; 17(3): 264-70.
125. Levine M, Goldstein JN. Emergency reversal of anticoagulation: novel agents. *Curr Neurol Neurosci Rep.* 2014; 14(8): 471.
126. Ageno W, Büller HR, Falanga A, Hacke W, Hendriks J, Lobban T, et al. Managing reversal of direct oral anticoagulants in emergency situations. Anticoagulation Education Task Force White Paper. *Thromb Haemost.* 2016; 116(6): 1003-10.
127. Heidbuchel H, Verhamme P, Alings M, Antz M, Diener HC, Hacke W, et al. Updated European Heart Rhythm Association Practical Guide on the use of non-vitamin K antagonist anticoagulants in patients with non-valvular atrial fibrillation. *Europace.* 2015; 17(10): 1467-507.
128. Eerenberg ES, Kamphuisen PW, Sijpkens MK, Meijers JC, Buller HR, Levi M. Reversal of rivaroxaban and dabigatran by prothrombin complex concentrate: a randomized, placebo-controlled, crossover study in healthy subjects. *Circulation.* 2011; 124(14): 1573-9.
129. Levi M, Moore KT, Castillejos CF, Kubitz D, Berkowitz SD, Goldhaber SZ, et al. Comparison of three-factor and four-factor prothrombin complex concentrates regarding reversal of the anticoagulant effects of rivaroxaban in healthy volunteers. *J Thromb Haemost.* 2014; 12(9): 1428-36.
130. Nagalla S, Thomson L, Oppong Y, Bachman B, Chervoneva I, Kraft WK. Reversibility of Apixaban Anticoagulation with a Four-Factor Prothrombin Complex Concentrate in Healthy Volunteers. *Clin Transl Sci.* 2016; 9(3): 176-80.
131. Zahir H, Brown KS, Vandell AG, Desai M, Maa JF, Dishy V, et al. Edoxaban effects on bleeding following punch biopsy and reversal by a 4-factor prothrombin complex concentrate. *Circulation.* 2015; 131(1): 82-90.
132. Majeed A, Eelde A, Agren A, Schulman S, Holmström M. Thromboembolic safety and efficacy of prothrombin complex concentrates in the emergency reversal of warfarin coagulopathy. *Thromb Res.* 2012; 129(2): 146-51.
133. Leissinger CA, Blatt PM, Hoots WK, Ewenstein B. Role of prothrombin complex concentrates in reversing warfarin anticoagulation: a review of the literature. *American journal of hematology.* 2008; 83(2): 137-43.
134. Aledort LM. Comparative thrombotic event incidence after infusion of recombinant factor VIIa versus factor VIII inhibitor bypass activity. *J Thromb Haemost.* 2004; 2(10): 1700-8.
135. Almegren M. Reversal of direct oral anticoagulants. *Vasc Health Risk Manag.* 2017; 13: 287-92.
136. Dibu JR, Weimer JM, Ahrens C, Manno E, Frontera JA. The Role of FEIBA in Reversing Novel Oral Anticoagulants in Intracerebral Hemorrhage. *Neurocrit Care.* 2016; 2.9-413 : (3)4
137. Nagakari K, Emmi M, Iba T. Prothrombin Time Tests for the Monitoring of Direct Oral Anticoagulants and Their Evaluation as Indicators of the Reversal Effect. *Clin Appl Thromb Hemost.* 2017; 23(6): 677-84.
138. Martin AC, Gouin-Thibault I, Siguret V, Mordohay A, Samama CM, Gaussem P, et al. Multimodal assessment of non-specific hemostatic agents for apixaban reversal. *J Thromb Haemost.* 2015; 13(3): 426-36.
139. Levi M, Levy JH, Andersen HF, Truloff D. Safety of recombinant activated factor VII in randomized clinical trials. *N Engl J Med.* 2010; 363(19): 1791-800.
140. Warkentin TE, Margetts P, Connolly SJ, Lamy A, Ricci C, Eikelboom JW. Recombinant factor VIIa (rFVIIa) and hemodialysis to manage massive dabigatran-associated postcardiac surgery bleeding. *Blood.* 2012; 119(9): 2172-4.
141. Stangier J, Rathgen K, Stähle H, Mazur D. Influence of renal impairment on the pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics of oral dabigatran etexilate: an open-label, parallel-group, single-centre study. *Clin Pharmacokinet.* 2010; 49(4): 259-68.
142. Khadzhyonov D, Wagner F, Formella S, Wiegert E, Moschetti V, Slowinski T, et al. Effective elimination of dabigatran by haemodialysis. A phase I single-centre study in patients with end-stage renal disease. *Thromb Haemost.* 2013; 605-596 : (4)109
143. Liesenfeld KH, Staab A, Härtter S, Formella S, Clemens A, Lehr T. Pharmacometric characterization of dabigatran hemodialysis. *Clin Pharmacokinet.* 2013; 52(6): 453-62.

144. Chang DN, Dager WE, Chin AI. Removal of dabigatran by hemodialysis. *Am J Kidney Dis.* 2013; 61(3): 487-9.
145. Parasrampur DA, Marbury T, Matsushima N, Chen S, Wickremasingha PK, He L, et al. Pharmacokinetics, safety, and tolerability of edoxaban in end-stage renal disease subjects undergoing haemodialysis. *Thromb Haemost.* 2015; 113(04): 719-27.
146. Schiele F, van Ryn J, Canada K, Newsome C, Sepulveda E, Park J, et al. A specific antidote for dabigatran: functional and structural characterization. *Blood.* 2013; 121(18): 3554-62.
147. January CT, Wann LS, Calkins H, Chen LY, Cigarroa JE, Cleveland JC, Jr., et al. 2019 AHA/ACC/HRS Focused Update of the 2014 AHA/ACC/HRS Guideline for the Management of Patients With Atrial Fibrillation: A Report of the American College of Cardiology/American Heart Association Task Force on Clinical Practice Guidelines and the Heart Rhythm Society. *J Am Coll Cardiol.* 2019; 74(1): 104-32.
148. Schiele F, van Ryn J, Canada K, Newsome C, Sepulveda E, Park J, et al. A specific antidote for dabigatran: functional and structural characterization. *Blood, The Journal of the American Society of Hematology.* 2013; 121(18): 3554-62.
149. Mujer MTP, Rai MP, Atti V, Dimaandal IL, Chan AS, Shrotriya S, et al. An Update on the Reversal of Non-Vitamin K Antagonist Oral Anticoagulants. *Adv Hematol.* 2020; 2020: 7636104.
150. Glund S, Stangier J, Schmohl M, Gansser D, Norris S, van Ryn J, et al. Safety, tolerability, and efficacy of idarucizumab for the reversal of the anticoagulant effect of dabigatran in healthy male volunteers: a randomised, placebo-controlled, double-blind phase 1 trial. *Lancet.* 2015; 386(9994): 680-90.
151. Glund S, Moschetti V, Norris S, Stangier J, Schmohl M, van Ryn J, et al. A randomised study in healthy volunteers to investigate the safety, tolerability and pharmacokinetics of idarucizumab, a specific antidote to dabigatran. *Thromb Haemost.* 2015; 113(5): 943-51.
152. Glund S, Moschetti V, Norris S, Stangier J, Schmohl M, van Ryn J, et al. A randomised study in healthy volunteers to investigate the safety, tolerability and pharmacokinetics of idarucizumab, a specific antidote to dabigatran. *Thromb Haemost.* 2015; 113(05): 943-51.
153. Jin C, Huang RJ, Peterson ED, Laskowitz DT, Hernandez AF, Federspiel JJ, et al. Intravenous tPA (Tissue-Type Plasminogen Activator) in Patients With Acute Ischemic Stroke Taking Non-Vitamin K Antagonist Oral Anticoagulants Preceding Stroke. *Stroke.* 2018; 49(9): 2237-40.
154. Lu G, DeGuzman FR, Hollenbach SJ, Karbarz MJ, Abe K, Lee G, et al. A specific antidote for reversal of anticoagulation by direct and indirect inhibitors of coagulation factor Xa. *Nat Med.* 2013; 19(4): 446-51.
155. Lip GYH, Weber C. Thrombosis and Haemostasis: Past, present and future. *Thromb Haemost.* 2017; 117(7): 1217-8.
156. Goldin M, Hughes GJ, Choudhary Z, Tariq S, Shafeeq H, Cohen J. Reversal of anticoagulation: therapeutic advances and clinical guidelines. *American Journal of Therapeutics.* 2018; 25(1): e44-e52.
157. Kaatz S, Bhansali H, Gibbs J, Lavender R, Mahan CE, Paje DG. Reversing factor Xa inhibitors - clinical utility of andexanet alfa. *J Blood Med.* 2017; 8: 141-9.
158. Portola Pharmaceuticals. Andexxa (coagulation factor Xa (recombinant), inactivated-zhzo). FDA; 2018; Available from: <http://www.fda.gov/>.
159. Connolly SJ, Crowther M, Eikelboom JW, Gibson CM, Curnutte JT, Lawrence JH, et al. Full Study Report of Andexanet Alfa for Bleeding Associated with Factor Xa Inhibitors. *New England Journal of Medicine.* 2019; 380(14): 1326-35.
160. Ansell J, Laulicht BE, Bakhru SH, Burnett A, Jiang X, Chen L, et al. Ciraparantag, an anticoagulant reversal drug: mechanism of action, pharmacokinetics, and reversal of anticoagulants. *Blood.* 2021; 137(1): 115-25.